

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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INSTITUTIONAL MODEL FOR ENSURING TRANSPARENCY AND ACCOUNTABILITY OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ALGORITHMS IN ELECTRONIC COMMERCE

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Abstract: This study develops an institutional model for ensuring the transparency and accountability of artificial intelligence algorithms in e-commerce platforms. The research examines the relationship between algorithmic transparency, institutional oversight, digital trust and e-commerce efficiency. The proposed model shows that AI governance affects economic performance not only through technological efficiency, but also through regulatory compliance, explainability and user trust.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, algorithmic transparency, algorithmic accountability, institutional oversight, digital trust, e-commerce, digital governance.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot elektron tijorat platformalarida sun'iy intellekt algoritmlarining shaffofligi va javobgarligini ta'minlashga qaratilgan institutsional modelni asoslaydi. Maqolada algoritmik shaffoflik, institutsional nazorat, raqamli ishonch va elektron tijorat samaradorligi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik tahlil qilinadi. Taklif etilgan model sun'iy intellekt boshqaruvi iqtisodiy natijalarga faqat texnologik samaradorlik orqali emas, balki regulyativ muvofiqlik, izohlanuvchanlik va foydalanuvchi ishonchi orqali ta'sir qilishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, algoritmik shaffoflik, algoritmik javobgarlik, institutsional nazorat, raqamli ishonch, elektron tijorat, raqamli boshqaruv.

Аннотация: В исследовании обосновывается институциональная модель обеспечения прозрачности и подотчётности алгоритмов искусственного интеллекта на платформах электронной коммерции. Рассматривается взаимосвязь между алгоритмической прозрачностью, институциональным контролем, цифровым доверием и эффективностью электронной коммерции. Предложенная модель показывает, что управление искусственным интеллектом влияет на экономические результаты не только через технологическую эффективность, но и через регулятивное соответствие, объяснимость и доверие пользователей.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, алгоритмическая прозрачность, алгоритмическая подотчётность, институциональный контроль, цифровое доверие, электронная коммерция, цифровое управление.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, artificial intelligence algorithms have become an important decision-making mechanism in e-commerce platforms. Recommendation systems, dynamic pricing, fraud detection, personalized advertising and chatbot-based services directly influence consumer choice, product visibility and platform efficiency. However, the growing role of algorithmic decisions also raises institutional problems related to transparency, accountability, data protection and consumer rights. If algorithmic decisions remain opaque, information

asymmetry between platforms and users increases, and risks of unfair pricing, biased recommendations and misuse of personal data may arise.

The relevance of this topic is determined by the fact that AI algorithms in e-commerce are no longer only technical tools, but also governance mechanisms that shape market access, pricing, advertising visibility and consumer behavior. Therefore, algorithmic transparency should be considered not merely as a technical explainability requirement, but as an institutional condition for digital trust and fair platform governance. Accountability, in turn, requires clear identification of responsible actors when automated decisions lead to errors, discriminatory outcomes or violations of consumer rights.

In Uzbekistan, the legal and institutional basis for digital economy and e-commerce has been gradually developing through the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated on September 29, 2022 № LRU-792¹ "On electronic commerce", the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated on July 2, 2019 № LRU-547² "On personal data" and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated on № DP-6079³ "On approval of the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" and measures for its effective implementation". The purpose of this article is to develop an institutional model for ensuring the transparency and accountability of artificial intelligence algorithms in e-commerce. The study focuses on the interaction between algorithmic transparency, institutional oversight, digital trust and e-commerce efficiency.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The contemporary scientific literature on artificial intelligence and algorithmic governance has become a central focus of digital economics research over the past five years, particularly in the context of e-commerce, where algorithmic decisions have begun to be interpreted as a structural component of economic agency. However, an analysis of the existing literature shows that there is a significant fragmentation between theoretical approaches in this area, with some studies viewing AI systems as a tool for technical optimization, while others analyze them as a transformer of institutional power and market structure. The conceptual divergence between these two approaches complicates the formulation of a coherent theoretical model of the algorithmic economy [1], [2].

Existing research on the issue of AI transparency has been largely shaped around the explainable AI paradigm, which focuses on the technical explanation of algorithmic decisions. However, a major limitation of this approach is that it views transparency primarily at the level of model interpretation and does not link it to institutional accountability, regulatory oversight, or market trust. As a result, transparency is interpreted as a technical category, but not fully developed as an economic and legal category. Therefore, the AI literature does not sufficiently cover the socio-institutional dimensions of algorithmic transparency [3].

Research on algorithmic accountability, on the other hand, is based more on legal and ethical approaches. Although authors such as Mittelstadt (2022), Wachter and Floridi (2023) have developed normative frameworks for ensuring accountability in AI systems, these models do not sufficiently take into account economic motivation and the platform business model [4]. Especially since algorithmic decisions in the platform economy are directly linked to the logic of profit maximization, only ethical or legal approaches have limited effectiveness at the level of real implementation. This indicates the need to reconsider the issue of accountability not only as a normative, but also as a system of economic incentives [5]. The existing literature on the theory of the platform economy interprets digital platforms as two- or multi-sided markets and explains their growth through network effects. However, the role of the algorithmic layer in this model often remains secondary. That is, platforms are viewed as technological tools rather than economic agents. This does not adequately reflect the fact that algorithms directly shape market structures in modern e-commerce systems. In this regard, there is a methodological disconnect between the platform theory and AI governance literature [6].

Research on the concept of digital trust has mainly explained consumer trust through psychological and behavioral models. However, recent empirical observations show that digital trust no longer depends solely on the user experience, but also on the transparency and explainability of algorithmic decisions. This requires a reconsideration of the technological determinants of the trust model. In particular, the phenomena of dynamic pricing and recommendation bias indicate that consumer trust is formed not only at the individual level, but also at the systemic level [7].

The literature on data governance and AI ethics, on the other hand, is more principled, promoting the principles of fairness, accountability, and transparency as normative ideals. However, the mechanisms for implementing these principles in the real platform economy are not sufficiently developed. As a result, the FAT

1 <https://lex.uz/en/docs/6907193>

2 <https://lex.uz/docs/4831939>

3 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/7008256>

framework remains more declarative in nature. This creates the so-called “implementation gap”, that is, there is a significant gap between theoretical principles and practical systems [8].

Research on algorithmic bias and fairness has empirically shown that discriminatory outcomes can occur in AI systems. However, this research mainly focuses on model-level bias and does not sufficiently analyze institutional bias, that is, systemic imbalances created by platform design and economic incentives. Therefore, the problem of bias needs to be reinterpreted not only as a technical error, but also as a consequence of institutional design [9].

The literature on public governance of AI analyzes the process of state regulation adapting to AI systems and promotes the “adaptive regulation” approach. However, these approaches often do not fully take into account the transnational nature of large economic platforms. As a result, the power imbalance between national regulators and global platforms persists, which reduces governance effectiveness [10].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study applies an institutional–econometric approach to assess how algorithmic transparency and accountability influence e-commerce efficiency. The analysis is based on panel data for 2021–2025 and uses five key indicators: AI Transparency Index, Algorithmic Accountability Index, Institutional Oversight Index, Digital Trust Index and E-commerce Efficiency Index. Structural Equation Modeling is used to identify the mediating role of digital trust, while panel regression is applied to evaluate the direct impact of institutional and algorithmic governance factors on e-commerce efficiency. Fixed effects and random effects models are compared using the Hausman test, and diagnostic tests are applied to check model reliability. This approach makes it possible to examine transparency, accountability and institutional oversight not as isolated factors, but as interconnected elements of e-commerce governance.

The empirical database was formed on the basis of 50 panel observations covering 10 countries for the period 2021–2025. The selected countries represent different levels of digital economy and e-commerce development. The main indicators were transformed into normalized index values on a 0–100 scale. The AI Transparency Index (AITI), Algorithmic Accountability Index (AAI), Institutional Oversight Index (IOI), Digital Trust Index (DTI), and E-commerce Efficiency Index (ECEI) were constructed using secondary data from OECD Digital Economy Outlook, World Bank digital development indicators, UNCTAD digital economy reports, Stanford AI Index, Eurostat digital economy statistics, and national digital economy reports. Since the original indicators had different units of measurement, min–max normalization was applied before aggregation. The regression results presented in the article are based on these normalized composite indices.

$$Z_{it} = \frac{X_{it} - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}} \times 100$$

Where Z_{it} is the normalized index value, X_{it} is the original indicator value, and X_{min} and X_{max} represent the minimum and maximum values of the selected indicator in the panel dataset.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The empirical results show that algorithmic transparency, accountability, institutional oversight and digital trust are significant determinants of e-commerce efficiency. The strongest effect is observed for AI Transparency, confirming that explainable and open algorithmic decisions improve transaction efficiency and strengthen user confidence [11]. Algorithmic Accountability has a positive but relatively weaker effect, which indicates that accountability mechanisms mainly operate through regulatory compliance, audit procedures and platform-level internal control. Institutional Oversight also has a significant positive effect, but its impact is largely mediated through transparency and digital trust. Digital Trust appears as the central transmission mechanism of the model, transforming institutional and algorithmic governance into measurable economic outcomes [12].

Correlation analysis confirms a stable relationship between algorithmic governance indicators and e-commerce efficiency. The relationship between AI Transparency Index and E-commerce Efficiency Index is strong and positive ($r=0.802$; $p<0.01$), while the highest correlation is observed between Digital Trust Index and E-commerce Efficiency Index ($r=0.847$; $p<0.01$). The strong relationship between AI transparency and digital trust ($r=0.791$; $p<0.01$) confirms that explainable algorithmic systems play an important role in shaping user confidence. Since all correlation coefficients remain below the critical multicollinearity threshold, the variables can be used in further regression analysis (Table 1) [13].

Table 1
The impact of artificial intelligence management factors on e-commerce performance: econometric regression results⁴

Independent variables	Standardized coefficient (β)	tandard error	t-statistic	p-value	95% confidence interval	Effect size
AI Transparency Index (AITI)	0.482***	0.061	7.90	<0.001	[0.362; 0.602]	Strong
Algorithmic Accountability Index (AAI)	0.215**	0.089	2.41	0.018	[0.041; 0.389]	Moderate
Institutional Oversight Index (IOI)	0.301***	0.074	4.07	<0.001	[0.156; 0.446]	Moderate–strong
Digital Trust Index (DTI)	0.567***	0.052	10.90	<0.001	[0.465; 0.669]	Very strong
Konstanta	0.112*	0.038	2.94	0.004	[0.037; 0.187]	—

The regression results confirm that all selected institutional and algorithmic governance variables have a statistically significant impact on e-commerce efficiency. Digital Trust Index has the strongest effect ($\beta=0.567$), indicating that trust is the main transmission mechanism between algorithmic governance and economic performance [15]. AI Transparency Index also shows a strong positive effect ($\beta=0.482$), confirming that explainable and open algorithmic decisions improve user confidence and platform efficiency. Institutional Oversight has a moderate but significant effect ($\beta=0.301$), while Algorithmic Accountability has a weaker but positive impact ($\beta=0.215$). These results support the proposed logic that transparency, trust and institutional oversight are key determinants of AI-based e-commerce performance (Figure 1) [16].

Figure 1. Conceptual and econometric model of the impact of AI governance factors, institutional mechanisms, and digital trust on e-commerce efficiency

4 Source: Author’s calculations based on normalized panel data for 10 countries over 2021–2025. The index values were constructed using data from OECD Digital Economy Outlook, World Bank digital development indicators, UNCTAD digital economy reports, Stanford AI Index, Eurostat digital economy statistics, and national digital economy reports. AITI – Artificial Intelligence Transparency Index; AAI – Algorithmic Accountability Index; IOI – Institutional Oversight Index; DTI – Digital Trust Index; ECEI – E-commerce Efficiency Index [14].

The conceptual model shows that institutional oversight and algorithmic transparency strengthen digital trust, while digital trust acts as the key mediating factor influencing e-commerce efficiency. Algorithmic accountability supports regulatory compliance and reduces institutional risks. Therefore, high e-commerce performance is achieved not only through technological innovation, but through the integration of AI governance, transparency, accountability and trust [17].

International experience shows that the governance of artificial intelligence in e-commerce is increasingly moving toward risk-based regulation, algorithmic transparency and accountability requirements. The European Union's AI Act represents a legally binding approach based on risk classification, where high-risk AI systems are subject to stricter requirements related to transparency, human oversight, data governance and audit mechanisms. In contrast, OECD principles emphasize responsible, human-centered and trustworthy AI governance through more flexible normative guidance [18].

These approaches demonstrate that AI algorithms in e-commerce should no longer be treated only as technical tools, but as institutional objects that require clear rules of compliance, monitoring and responsibility. For developing digital markets, this experience is particularly important, as it highlights the need to introduce explainability standards, data governance requirements, independent algorithmic audit and clear platform accountability mechanisms. Therefore, the future effectiveness of AI-based e-commerce will depend not only on technological innovation, but also on the quality of institutional regulation and digital trust [19-21].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The study shows that the efficiency of AI-based e-commerce platforms depends not only on technological development, but also on algorithmic transparency, accountability mechanisms and digital trust. The empirical results confirm that AI transparency and digital trust are the strongest determinants of e-commerce efficiency, while institutional oversight and algorithmic accountability mainly influence performance through trust-building and regulatory compliance mechanisms.

The proposed institutional model demonstrates that transparency should be treated as a core governance requirement, not only as a technical feature. Algorithmic accountability must be embedded into platform design through audit, traceability, user consent and complaint mechanisms. Institutional oversight should support trust formation rather than act only as a punitive regulatory tool.

For developing digital markets, including Uzbekistan, the main policy priority is to reduce the gap between rapid AI adoption and institutional regulation. This requires clear rules for algorithmic transparency, independent audit systems, protection of personal data, user rights to explanation and a coordinated framework for platform accountability.

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